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CASE REPORT

MASSIVE ASCITES OF UNKNOWN ORIGIN IN A YOUNG WOMAN: A CASE REPORT ON A DIAGNOSTIC DILEMMA FOR THE FAMILY PHYSICIAN

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ABSTRACT

Ascites is most commonly associated with chronic liver disease, malignancy, cardiac failure, or nephrotic syndrome. Idiopathic ascites in young adults without predisposing risk factors is rare and diagnostically challenging. We report the case of a 29-year-old nulliparous woman who presented with progressive abdominal distension and weight loss. Extensive laboratory evaluation, imaging studies, ascitic fluid analysis, and tumour marker assessment failed to reveal a definitive cause. A transient right pleural effusion and mildly elevated CA-125 raised suspicion for Meigs' syndrome; however, no ovarian mass was identified. After approximately five months of persistent ascites and multidisciplinary management, the condition resolved spontaneously without definitive therapy. This case highlights the complexity of evaluating ascites in low-risk young patients and underscores the importance of coordinated primary care, careful diagnostic stewardship, and longitudinal follow-up when investigations remain inconclusive.

Keywords: Ascites, Idiopathic ascites, Young adult female, Diagnostic dilemma, Family physician, Spontaneous resolution

INTRODUCTION

Ascites refers to the pathological accumulation of fluid within the peritoneal cavity and is rarely a primary diagnosis. It typically occur secondary to systemic disease processes such as liver cirrhosis, malignancy, nephrotic syndrome, cardiac failure, or intra-abdominal infection (Rahil and Janice, 2023). Chronic liver disease accounts for the majority of cases worldwide and represents the most common cause encountered in primary care practice (Giulia-Anna, 2013).

In younger individuals, nephrotic syndrome remains an important differential diagnosis (Adarsh, Sanjiv and Rajesh, 2025). When ascites develops in a young adult without obvious risk factors or underlying chronic disease, diagnostic evaluation can become prolonged and resource-intensive. We present a case of massive ascites of unknown origin in a 29-year-old woman that persisted for several months before spontaneous resolution.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 29-year-old female trader presented in April 2025 with progressive abdominal distension and weight loss of one month's duration. The abdominal swelling developed gradually and was preceded by severe dysmenorrhoea and a brief febrile episode that resolved spontaneously. Two days after the onset of abdominal distension, she experienced non-bloody, non-mucoid diarrhoea lasting approximately 72 hours, with about nine to ten episodes in total. She denied jaundice, pruritus, vomiting, hematemesis, melena, constipation, early satiety, lower limb swelling, dyspnoea, orthopnoea, urinary symptoms, or constitutional features suggestive of tuberculosis.

There was no history of alcohol consumption, intravenous drug use, herbal medication use, or ovulation induction therapy. She had no family history of ovarian, endometrial, colorectal, or breast cancer. She was sexually active with a single same-sex partner. Her menstrual history was notable for regular 28-day cycles lasting four days, with dysmenorrhoea but no menorrhagia or dyspareunia. She was nulliparous (P0+2).

On examination, she was conscious, afebrile, anicteric, and haemodynamically stable. Her body mass index was 26.1 kg/m². The abdomen was distended with an abdominal girth of 96 cm, soft, and mildly tender in the right upper quadrant. Mild hepatomegaly and splenomegaly, each approximately 2 cm below the respective costal margins, were noted. There were no stigmata of chronic liver disease, no pedal oedema, and no features suggestive of cardiac failure.

INVESTIGATIONS

Initial laboratory investigations revealed mild anaemia (PCV 33%) and an elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (71 mm/hr). Liver function tests showed mildly elevated total and conjugated bilirubin and slightly elevated alkaline phosphatase, with normal transaminases. Renal function and electrolytes were normal. Viral serology, including hepatitis B surface antigen, hepatitis C antibody, and retroviral screening, was non-reactive.

Abdominopelvic ultrasound demonstrated massive ascites with free-floating bowel loops and mild splenomegaly but normal liver echotexture and no focal hepatic lesions. The uterus and adnexa appeared normal. There was no intra-abdominal lymphadenopathy. Ascitic fluid analysis revealed inflammatory cells on cytology. GeneXpert testing for tuberculosis was negative. Serum protein and ascitic biochemistry did not reveal a definitive cause. Further evaluation included computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging of the abdomen and pelvis. These confirmed severe ascites and identified a simple right ovarian cyst but no ovarian tumour or intra-abdominal mass. Magnetic resonance imaging also demonstrated a right pleural effusion. Serum CA-125 was mildly elevated at 40.8 IU. Despite extensive evaluation, no definitive diagnosis was established.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Given the global predominance of chronic liver disease as a cause of ascites, cirrhosis and primary liver malignancy were initially considered (Rahil and Janice, 2023; Giulia-Anna, 2013). However, the absence of risk factors, normal liver architecture on imaging, and lack of biochemical evidence of hepatic dysfunction argued against these diagnoses. Nephrotic syndrome was considered due to the patient's age, as it can present with effusion in younger populations (Adarsh, Sanjiv and Rajesh, 2025). This was excluded by the absence of proteinuria, hypoalbuminaemia, and peripheral oedema.

The presence of ascites and pleural effusion with mildly elevated CA-125 prompted consideration of Meigs' syndrome. Meigs' syndrome is characterised by ascites and pleural effusion associated with benign ovarian tumours and may demonstrate elevated CA-125 levels (Liqin *et al.*, 2024). However, repeated imaging did not identify an ovarian fibroma or fibrothecoma, and spontaneous resolution without surgical intervention made this diagnosis unlikely.

Endometriosis-associated ascites, though rare, has been documented in young Nigerian women (Abiodun *et al.*, 2023). While the initial symptoms followed menstruation, imaging and clinical findings did not support advanced endometriosis. Reports of ascites of unexplained origin exist in the literature. Muteb and Ahmad (2022) described a case of unexplained ascites after extensive negative investigations. Similarly, Magdalena, Jolanta and Magdalena (2020) reported massive ascites of unknown origin that resolved spontaneously. These cases support the possibility of idiopathic ascites with benign outcomes.

MANAGEMENT

The patient was commenced on spironolactone 100 mg daily and furosemide 40 mg daily for symptomatic control. Neomycin was prescribed initially, and later, antibiotics were administered during a febrile episode. She was co-managed by a multidisciplinary team including family medicine, gastroenterology, gynaecology, radiology, and pathology specialists. Despite several months of follow-up and repeated evaluations, the ascites persisted without progression to systemic deterioration.

CLINICAL OUTCOME

Several weeks after defaulting from follow-up and discontinuing medications, the patient returned reporting complete and spontaneous resolution of abdominal distension. Clinical examination confirmed absence of ascites. She resumed normal daily activities and remained clinically stable.

DISCUSSION

Ascites most commonly arises from cirrhosis and portal hypertension (Rahil and Janice, 2023; Giulia-Anna, 2013). In younger individuals, nephrotic syndrome represents an important differential diagnosis (Adarsh, Sanjiv and Rajesh, 2025). The absence of clinical, biochemical and radiologic features of these conditions in this patient underscores the unusual nature of this case. Meigs' syndrome was strongly considered due to the presence of pleural effusion and elevated CA-125; however, absence of an ovarian tumour excluded this diagnosis (Liqin *et al.*, 2024). Endometriosis-associated ascites has been documented in West Africa (Abiodun *et al.*, 2023), but the lack of confirmatory findings made this unlikely. Cases of idiopathic ascites with spontaneous resolution have been described (Muteb and Ahmad, 2022; Magdalena *et al.*, 2020).

The mechanism remains uncertain but may involve transient inflammatory, infectious, or immunologically mediated peritoneal processes. This case also highlights the psychosocial and financial impact of prolonged undiagnosed illness. The patient experienced economic strain and social stigma. The family physician played a pivotal role in coordinating multidisciplinary care, providing reassurance, and ensuring continuity—core principles in primary care management (Giulia-Anna, 2013). Conclusion Massive ascites of unknown origin in a young, otherwise healthy woman is rare and diagnostically challenging. Even after extensive evaluation, a definitive cause may not be identified.

This case demonstrates that idiopathic ascites may resolve spontaneously and follow a benign course. Careful monitoring, multidisciplinary collaboration, and patient-centred reassurance remain essential when investigations are inconclusive. Further research exploring transient inflammatory or hormonally mediated mechanisms in reproductive-aged women is warranted.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Clinicians should prioritise common causes of ascites such as chronic liver disease, malignancy, cardiac failure, and nephrotic syndrome during initial evaluation.

2. Abdominal ultrasound and ascitic fluid analysis should be undertaken promptly to guide further investigations and narrow differential diagnoses.
3. Urinalysis and serum protein assessment should be routine in young individuals to rule out nephrotic syndrome, which may present with effusions.
4. Mild elevation of CA-125 should not be assumed to indicate malignancy, as it may occur in benign gynaecological conditions such as Meigs' syndrome.
5. Endometriosis-associated ascites, although uncommon, should be included in the differential diagnosis, particularly in regions where cases have been reported.
6. In cases where extensive evaluation is negative and the patient remains clinically stable, clinicians should acknowledge that ascites of unknown origin has been documented.
7. Given reports of spontaneous resolution, a period of careful monitoring may be appropriate when no progressive pathology is identified.
8. Coordinated care involving family physicians, gastroenterologists, gynaecologists, radiologists, and pathologists improves diagnostic oversight and patient support.
9. Family physicians should address the emotional and economic burden of prolonged undiagnosed illness through reassurance and continuity of care.
10. Prospective reporting of similar cases may help clarify mechanisms underlying idiopathic ascites and improve evidence-based management.

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